

Ontology-based Learning Content Management System

Nwe Ni Win*

Abstract

The paper explains the Ontology-based Learning Content Management System. A Content Management System (CMS) specialized for the needs of the ontology-driven environment. With this approach, content is also structured according to the ontologies, meaning that every concept in the ontology is connected to a specific piece of content, describing details or relations of the concept with other items in the same ontology. Ontologies have the potential to play an important role in instructional design and the development of course content. They can be used to represent knowledge about content, supporting instructors in creating content or learners in accessing content in a knowledge-guided way.

Keywords: e-Learning, Content Management Systems (CMS), Learning Content Management System (LCMS), Virtual Learning Environment (VLE)

Introduction

As a result of the rapid development of the information and communication technologies and their increasing relevance in all aspects of our living, the role of e-learning systems increases too. The success of this platform depends on its involving into the integrated solution of the information systems at universities. Content management systems (CMS) provide an integrated framework, based on metadata and workflows, for organizing and sharing information resources within a community of users. Ontologies, adding the required semantics to vocabularies of concepts, may considerably improve the classification and search paradigms. It is much easier to identify the right description tags exploiting semantic relationships between ontology concepts, rather than looking up in a long list of keywords provided by a metadata vocabulary. Also, ontologies may integrate different views of a knowledge domain, enabling different users to reach the same concept going through different semantic paths.

Background Theory

Content Management System

Ontology is a discipline that is part of the knowledge representation field. Ontology defines the kinds of things that exist in an application domain. In the computing context, an ontology is a framework for representing concepts and the relationships that exist between those concepts. In ontology, a precise definition is associated with each concept and relationship that is used. Ontology technology is considered to be a highly suitable means of supporting educational-technology systems. There are numerous areas where the use of ontologies would prove that it is useful for the Web. One scenario is to allow Web tools to gather information that has more clearly defined meaning and, in this way, matched the users' needs more closely. Another scenario is an application of ontology as a discipline in teaching and learning context in order to structure the subject domain of interest as a set of concepts that are connected by defined relationships. Learning content allows learners to acquire knowledge about a subject, i.e. knowledge is an intrinsic, although often implicit aspect of content.

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Ontologies for educational content add flexibility through the explicit separation of knowledge and content.

Learning Content Management System

E-learning systems build up a platform for the realization of new study forms (especially the distance mode). E-learning system is a complex, data system primarily is determined for the support of the pure set of e-learning activities. These activities include not only study activities, but also managing activities and governing of study courses. Generally, it means the integration of kind of systems as Learning Content Management Systems (LCMS), virtual learning environment (VLE) or communication portals into one complex system. Students are faced with the situation where they must use few practically independent separated systems and make endless authorizations, uploads or imports.

Comparison with LMS and LCMS

The focus of an LMS is to deliver online courses or training to learners, while managing students and keeping track of their progress and performance across all types of training activities. An LMS is not used to create course content. A learning [content management system](#) (LCMS) is a related software technology that provides a multi-user environment where developers, authors, instructional designers, and subject matter experts may create, store, reuse, manage, and deliver digital [e-learning](#) content from a central object repository. LCMS focuses on the development, management and publishing of the content that will typically be delivered via an LMS. Users can both create and re-use e-learning content and reduce duplicated development efforts.

LCMSs provide tools for authoring and reusing or re-purposing content ([mutated learning objects](#), or MLOs) as well as virtual spaces for student interaction (such as discussion forums, live chat rooms and live web-conferences). LCMS technology can either be used in tandem with an LMS, or as a standalone application for learning initiatives that require rapid development and distribution of learning content.

LCMS Conceptual Design and Architecture

Conceptual Design

Figure.1. LCMS's Conceptual Design

An overview of principal components of the LCMS application modular architecture is given in Figure.1. The implementation is split into different parts:

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LCMS Conceptual Design and Architecture

Conceptual Design

- 1) LCMS.Common –used for defining application entities (eg.; Users, Courses, Resources)
- 2) CMS.Operational –used from application for mail operations;
- 3) LCMS.Business Logic –is responsible for all actions that are going on behind the scene;
- 4) LCMS.Data Tier – is used from LCMS’s Business Logic for extracting and storing data.

While the basic role of a CMS is usually to display content to [end users](#) in their [web browser](#), additional functionality may aid in content distribution to other computer systems, e-mail distribution, such as content distribution through newsletters, is another common CMS feature: e-mails may be template, and mailing lists manage, through the system. These may include automatic links back to content on the web site.

LCMS’s Architecture

Figure.2. The LCMS’s architecture

Today’s most web-based applications use three tier client/server models. This approach clearly divides the presentation layer from content and data storage. This kind of system decomposition enables us develop large-scale software systems and reduce overall development time. Using this approach, the application’s architecture would be like in Figure.2.

The Development of Ontologies

Taxonomy and Ontology

Taxonomy is a way of classifying or categorizing a set of things using a hierarchical structure, which is a treelike structure, with the most general category as the root of the tree. Each node, including the root node, is an information entity that represents some object in the real world that is being modeled. Each link between two nodes in a taxonomy represents a “subclassification-of” relation or a “superclassification-of” relationship. An ontology-based content for learning defines the terms are used to describe and represent an area of knowledge. Ontologies include computer-usable definitions of basic concepts in the domain and the relationships among those concepts. Ontology-based learning need to specify descriptions for the following kinds of concepts: Classes (general things) in the many domains of interest. The relationships can exist among things. The properties (or attributes) may have in the Classes.

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Functionality

While LMS and LCMS products have different strengths and weaknesses, they generally address the following areas of functionality:

A. LMS Functionality

- Student Registration and Administration
- Training Event Management (i.e., scheduling, tracking, and WBT delivery)
- Curriculum and Certification Management
- Skills and Competencies Management
- Reporting
- Training Record Management
- Courseware Authoring

B. LCMS Functionality

- Template-driven, Collaborative Content Development
- Facilitated Content Management (i.e., indexing and reuse)
- Publishing
- Workflow Integration
- Automated Interface with an LM

Input Data for Student and Teacher Submission

In this section the modules of the system is presented. The key feature of today's LCMS is included in the first stage of the system development and in the next stage the system will be probably upgraded with new additional modules.

A. User Management

The user management modules and their main functionalities are:

(1) Enrollment

Students are enrolled automatically from another existing University Schedule system. Teachers and administrators can move students to another group if necessary.

Roles

Roles for specific participants can define for each course and resource. Instructors can assign user roles to other users enrolled to the course. Instructors can create content and assign privileges.

B. Course Management

(1) Assignment Module

Assignments can be specified with a due date and a maximum grade. Students can upload their assignments (any file format) to the server - they are date-stamped.

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(2) Lesson Module

The following descriptions address the organization and control of learning and teaching processes for ontology- based for e-learning Content Management System.

For the hierarchy of ontologies, a level structure is proposed to reach the intended knowledge. Its purpose is to define the scheme for an ontology-based realization of the order of learning content to achieve an optimal learning result as well as the description of computer science course. Actors' (teacher and students) experiences with the learning and teaching processes can be integrated in those ontologies. These implicit quality aspects result in a substantial quality gain.

Classes

In Figure.3, the **Classes** tab shows the ontology classes that have been defined. Ontology classes are very similar to classes in an object oriented program. Just like in object oriented programming classes in ontologies form a hierarchy. You can view this hierarchy on the right hand panel labeled *Asserted class hierarchy*. The root class which is at the top of the inheritance hierarchy is **Thing** (this is true of all OWL ontologies). If you click the triangle next to **Thing** you will see the classes that are descended from **Thing**. Click the triangle next to **Computer-Science** to see the classes descended from **Computer-Science**.

Equivalent classes: This section describes other classes or groups that are equivalent to the selected class. In the case of **First Year**, **Second Year**, **Third Year**, **1st Year Honour**, **2nd Year Honour**, etc.; these are equivalent classes.

Superclasses: These are the parent class(es) of the selected class (remember- since you can have multiple classes you can also have multiple superclasses). Right now there is no superclasses for **Computer-Science**, even though the Asserted class hierarchy has it under Person.

Members: This shows those individuals which are members of this class. They can be added explicitly here, or inferred later through reasoning.

Browse through the classes provided and try to get a feel for the concepts they are trying to describe. After you have done looking at the classes go to the top menu and select

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Reasoner -> Fact++. This will turn on the reasoner to infer additional facts about the classes. The left panel switches to *Inferred class hierarchy* from *Asserted class hierarchy* automatically but you can click either tab switch back and forth between the views. Click on the class **First Year**, you'll notice that **First_Sem and Second_Sem** have been added as a superclass. Then Click the triangle next to **First_Sem** to see the subclasses descended from **First_Sem**.

Common Usage: It is custom to create classes with nouns as their names, since this is what they represent. It is also custom to make capitalize class names- if they are multiple words capitalize each one.

Figure 4. OWL Visualization of Computer Science Course (Asserted Model)

Figure 5. OWL Visualization of Computer Science Course (Sub-link)

Reasoner -> Fact++. This will turn on the reasoner to infer additional facts about the model. The left panel switches to *Inferred class hierarchy* from *Asserted class hierarchy* but you can click either tab switch back and forth between the views. Click on the **2nd Year**, you'll notice that **First_Sem** and **Second_Sem** have been added as subclasses. Click the triangle next to **First_Sem** to see the subclasses descended from **First_Sem**!

Common Usage: It is custom to create classes with nouns as their names, since they represent things. It is also custom to make class names capitalize each one.

Figure 4. OWL Visualization of Computer Science Course (Asserted Model)

Figure.6. Searching

Conclusion

Ontologies have been used in various educational-technology systems. In particular, they can capture the knowledge aspects of educational content. However, ontologies for a particular subject may not exist or it might be unclear if existing ones are suitable. Ontology-based Content Management System addresses how content ontologies should appear with regard to their structure and quality, and how to develop content ontologies for educational technology. The ontology can provide an interface to the content. The ontology can guide the instruction design of a course. Learners (or instructors) can browse through the content guided by the dependencies expressed in the concept ontology, thus allowing for the delivery of a course in a way that matches the preferred learning style of the user by varying the sequentialization of content elements. A combination of a concept ontology and associated content can also be used to generate a separate content representation.

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